

Maladaptive daydreaming

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Abstract:

Nowadays, many people are suffering from a spreading condition called daydreaming. Daydreaming is a state of unconsciousness where you spend long time thinking about things that you would like to do or have happened to you. Lately, daydreaming has become a widely spreading problem as many people are suffering from it. According to prior research papers, about seventy percent of students are suffering from this condition. So, the purpose of this study was to investigate daydreaming and its effects among students to ensure the reliability of hypothesizing that daydreaming has negative impacts on productivity. That was through making a survey on a sample of 40 students aging from 16 to 18 years old, using different types of questions to know whether they suffer from daydreaming, its effect if positive or negative, and to what extent does it affect them. After the survey was done, results showed the reliability of the hypothesis as it was found that 85 percent of the sample are immersed in daydreaming and about 40 percent of them spend up to three to four hours daydreaming daily. The results also showed that about 47.5 percent of them lose their emotions in reality as they used it up in their daydreams, and about 55 percent put off and procrastinate their tasks and thus daydreaming interfere with their academic and occupational success. Finally the results showed that daydreaming negatively affected them to an extent of 10 to 12 degree in a twelve-degree scale. It is recommended that the next steps or researches in this area is to investigate direct solutions for dealing with daydreaming and avoiding its negative impacts.

Introduction:

Maladaptive daydreaming is considered as a condition where a person goes deep with his thoughts forgetting what he was doing at reality for a while, then he returns back to reality. Also, it is something that most of people do regularly in their life. By observation, maladaptive daydreaming is most common between students at schools or colleges. As, the estimated data of prevalence of daydreaming between students is about 70% of them. Furthermore, daydreaming probably takes hours and that's affects person's productivity. For example, if a student is studying then he does daydreaming unconsciously and lays his studying aside then he comes back, after coming he will observe some impacts such as losing concentration, feeling empty or down, having low energy and wasting his time. As a results of these impacts the person or student will suffer from low production and may develop mental health problems.

Definition of terms:

- **Maladaptive daydreaming (shortened to MD):**

MD is a condition of Unconsciousness and being lost at your thought while you are doing a particular task. MD may tend to be stories of happiness, sadness, or feeling that you achieved all what you want. Furthermore, MD is common between children and students as they have

a lot to do and more spare time. As mentioned at pervious study that maladaptive daydreamers may spend 4.5 hours of their day distracted by their daydreams.

- **Productivity and MD :**

As usual as daydreaming has some positive effects such as increasing creativity, it has several negative impacts. For example, weaken daydreamer’s relationships, work or school performance, sleep, and daily life imbalance. The most important negative impact that has to be discussed is low productivity. As, Studies of medical students have found that those who engaged in maladaptive daydreaming reported a significant decline in their GPA. And that is due to multiple reasons like feeling low, consuming their emotions or wasting their time.

Citation:

- *Maladaptive daydreaming: Symptoms and diagnosis | sleep foundation.* Sleep Foundation. (2022)
- A., Says:, S., says:, F. A., says:, M.-A. S., says:, L., says:, J., & says:, H. (2020). *People with "Maladaptive daydreaming" spend an average of four hours a day lost in their imagination.*

Body:

Methodology:

After sharing the survey, the following characteristics of the sample participants have been found:

Description of the sample participants:

- Ages: the common age among participants lies between 15 to 22 as illustrated in fig (1).

Figure 1(Ages of participants)

- Level of education: About half of the participants are at college and the other half at prep or high schools as illustrated in fig (2).

Figure 2(Education level)

- Gender: about 77.5% of participants are females and 22.5% are males as illustrated in fig (3).

Figure 3(Genders)

Description of the questionnaire:

The questionnaire is divided into two sections: the first one was for testing the hypothesis and the second was for demographic section. Additionally the questions are classified into 4 questions. These questions are :

- **Yes/No questions:** these questions were designed to test if the samples have the daydreaming problem. (First & Forth questions)
- **Multiple choice questions:** The second & fifth & sixth questions are multiple choice questions. These questions were designed to know more details about the cases that suffer from daydreaming.
- **Checklist questions:** Checklist question is shown in the third question and this question were designed to know the symptoms that participants suffer after they do daydreaming.
- **Scale questions:** the seventh question is a scale question and this question is about showing the extent of having negative impacts result from daydreaming.
- **Open ended questions:** Open ended question is shown in the last question. This question is to know about the best ways to defeat the daydreaming problems.

Findings:

- The first question that reads” Do you ever spend hours doing nothing but daydreaming?” There was an equalization state in the percentage of responses (42.5%) between two types of people: As a percentage of 42.5 were found to day dream frequently and the same percent occasionally daydream and that is illustrated in fig (4).

Figure 4(First question analysis)

- In the second question that reads: “How many hours do you spend daydreaming?” Its result indicates that the most percent of responses (40%) spends from two to three hours per day doing day dreaming as illustrated in fig (5).

Figure 5(Second question analysis)

- In the third question that reads: “Do you experience any of these symptoms while daydreaming?” There are three observations illustrated in fig (6) from this investigating question:

Figure 6(Third question analysis)

- 75% of responses Laugh because of happy daydream content.
- 57.5% of responses find difficulty focusing on daily tasks.
- Two responses have the same percent (55%): Literally accomplishing absolutely nothing and crying because of upsetting/moving daydream content.

- In the fourth question that reads: “Do you feel like an emotional zombie (Without emotions) in real life because your emotions are all used up in your daydreams?” The chart in fig (7) shows that the 47.5% agree and 50% disagree, this percent can seem small, but it is large as it is almost equal the percent of disagree. It is also supported by

Figure 7(Fourth question analysis)

(Maladaptive daydreaming as a new form of behavioral addiction). One of the results of this research paper says: “He thinks he was overly stressed and lacked emotional support, which discouraged him from interaction with others and expressing his needs”. This person is called peter who the methods’ procedures to get rid of day dreaming are applied on him.

5. In the fifth question reading: “Do you ever confuse your daydreams with real life?” In other words,” do you ever believe characters or events in your daydreams are real?” There are two contradicting percentages illustrated in fig(8):

Figure 8(Fifth question analysis)

- 40% Yes, sometimes I think my characters or events in my daydreams are real.
- 55% No, I can tell the difference between my daydreams and real life.

These results are supported by (Maladaptive daydreaming as a new form of behavioral addiction). One of the results shows how the person who does daydreaming is afraid from losing the feeling of reality by overlapping and repetition of character. It says that: “It started by the second grade but did not bother me then it is bothering now so much. Now I fear that I have wasted my life and opportunities”. Although daydreaming is pleasurable, he says he has developed a “delusional personality” and lost control over fantasizing, becoming afraid of losing touch with reality or that the another imagined negative side will take over”.

6. In the sixth question that reads “Does your daydreaming interfere with your academic/occupational success?” After seeing the responses the highest percent (45%) agrees with “No, my daydreaming does not interfere with my job or academic life” as illustrated in fig(9). This percentage is supported by (Impact of

Figure 9(Sixth question analysis)

Maladaptive Daydreaming on Grade Point Average (GPA) and the Association between Maladaptive Daydreaming and Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD)).These research papers’ results show the relationship between the stress and daydreaming and their effects on productivity, academic performance and GPA of the medical students. DM is

a reason for GAD and stress that will decrease the productivity and the focus of the person.

7. In the seventh question that reads” To what extent do you feel that you daydreams negatively impact you?” The results can be seen obviously by the graph in fig(10) .

Figure 10(Seventh question analysis)

8. In the eighth question that reads “What’s the most effective way(s) for you to pull yourself out of a daydream when you need to deal with real life?”

- The opinions of the people were:
- بشغل وقتي بحاجات اهم واخصلي وقت معين واوظفه في الكتابه او رسم
- Sleep well
- I am working on myself to pull out all my daydreams but it is really difficult. sometimes I think that I got rid of it but the fact that it is done when I am working well in my life but when I fail or get disappointment, I return again to dream and think about achieving what I am could not achieve in the real life.
- Sometimes i write down all thoughts inside my brain and set a timer to help me at concentration.
- اقدر افكر ب جديه اكثر ف الموضوع ب حيث انك تقدر تفرق بين الواقع والحلم
- Writing down what I want to accomplish for the day and try to get things done.
- انتبه ف المذاكره من غير مشتت دماغي او اعمل اي حاجه بحبها+تنظيم الوق

Conclusion:

As illustrated from the results, the hypothesis was supported. The answers of most questions supported the hypothesis principles as it was found that about 85% of the sample participants were suffering from daydreaming. In the third question it was found that the majority of responses of sample members gave actions like laughing while daydreaming because of happy daydreams content, this supports our hypothesis that by dreaming you will lose the ability of doing anything that can help you reach your dream, because you already have reached it by day dreams. The results of the fourth question delivered high percent of responses raising our estimations as a lot of people lose their emotions in reality by day dreaming because they have already exhausted their emotions. In the sixth question a lot of responses agree that they can procrastinate by daydreaming, this will separate between them and their target. Finally, it was confirmed that daydreaming has huge negative effects on productivity by 85% from every 40 person.

Recommendation:

For those who suffer from daydreaming, the following points are recommended:

- 1- Identify your daydreaming triggers. You can make notes about when you do daydreaming, and what was happening right before.
- 2- Stay engaged during the day. Keep your mind busy and unavailable for daydreaming. Choose tasks that increase your focus, like reading or crosswords or games that have an aim. This method of treatment is supported by (Maladaptive daydreaming as a new form of behavioral addiction). One of the results of this research paper supports this recommendation as person who want to destroy day dreaming says: "I spend about 14 hours a day surfing on my computer, watching pictures of cars, YouTube, and wanking. Political news, for example, may trigger delusional fantasies in which I am a multimillionaire who would never let that situation happen".
- 3- Try to make your daydreaming productive. Once you've started noticing your daydreams and what triggers them, begin to pay attention to how they make you feel. You may notice that some make you anxious while others get you motivated. If you have the same daydreams, motivating you to do something, consider working towards making the goal of the dream happen.

For who would like to continue with the study, the following points are recommended:

1. The next steps or researches in this area is to investigate direct solutions for dealing with daydreaming and avoiding its negative impacts.

2. The analysis of responses suggest the existence of a relation between daydreaming and mental pressure as the highest percent was among students , so it will be an effective area of investigation for the incoming steps.

APA Citation (references):

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